

Introduction

Any successful endodontic therapy requires elimination of the endodontic biofilms through meticulous root canal disinfection methods. Sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) are the most common effective irrigants, in removing smear-layer from the coronal and middle thirds of the dental canals but reduced considerably towards the apical one third. The traditional method of irrigation using a syringe with a needle often fails in adequate delivery and penetration of irrigant solutions within the complex three – dimensional microstructure of the canal system, as the fluid penetration in the apical third and beyond the main canal is limited. Bacteria remaining after chemo-mechanical preparation are usually found in isthmuses, lateral canals and apical ramifications inaccessible to standard instrumentation and irrigation . Therefore, irrigant activation techniques have been suggested to improve their distribution in the canal system and increase irrigation effectiveness. Laser-activated irrigation (LAI) has been proposed as an alternative method to release the irrigant more deeply, thereby increasing the cleaning ability inside the root canal system. The Er:YAG laser (Erbium, Yttrium-Aluminium-Garnet) emitting at 2940 nm and the Er,Cr:YSGG laser (Erbium; Chromium, Yttrium-Scandium-Gallium-Garnet) emitting at 2780 nm, are both suitable for LAI, since these wavelengths are close to the absorption peak of water. The effect of LAI is further influenced by laser characteristics such as pulse length, pulse energy, pulse frequency, laser tip design and position. The cleaning mechanism of LAI depends on rapid fluid motion in the canal as a result of expansion and implosion of vapour bubbles at the fibre tip caused by the pulsed laser operation, a pure cavitation phenomenon hock waves and secondary cavitation bubbles are believed to contribute to the cleaning action.

Materials & Methods

The electronic databases PubMed (full text and English abstract in vivo, ex vivo and in vitro) was searched from 2016 to 2022, using the search terms as follows: “biofilm; endodontics, laser, laser-activated irrigation; root canal irrigation”. Only clinical studies on teeth with closed apices were chosen. The exclusion criteria were as follows: studies related to other branches of dentistry (implantology, periodontics, or surgery), literature and systemic reviews, commentaries, interviews, updates and short communications. After application of all inclusion and exclusion criteria, seven papers were reviewed critically.

Discussion

The results of the study by Meyer *et al.* indicate the stronger mechanical effect of LAI compared to UAI and SI, which is attributed to the extremely turbulent action of the irrigant induced by pulsed erbium lasers. Interestingly, a higher pulse energy (40 instead of 20mJ) and a deeper position of the fibre tip inside the canal (6 mm from working length instead of at the canal entrance), significantly increased the bacterial reduction. The effect of higher pulse energy can probably be explained by the resulting higher peak powers which yield larger primary cavitation bubbles at the fibre tip and hence greater liquid displacement and more violent shock waves. Moreover, The study was performed by Race J *et al* showed that mechanical instrumentation with 4% NaOCl and 15% EDTAC combined with LAI 0.75W was not significantly more effective at removing bacteria. Compared to the UAI and LAI 0.5W groups, SEM qualitative analysis showed that there were co-aggregated bacteria and small areas of biofilm remaining in the LAI 0.75 W group.

This is a surprising result and may have occurred because LAI (0.75 W) fluid dynamics did not improve the flow of 4% NaOCl into the deeper recesses of the root canal system. Interestingly, LAI 0.5 W was more effective at removing bacteria than LAI 0.75 W. The reason for this may be due to the methodology used in the study. An explanation might be that the increased laser power setting caused the irrigating solution to spray out of the canal because there was no coronal reservoir to stop this from occurring. By not having the tip of the laser fully immersed in irrigating solution, effective cavitation may have not occurred, thereby limiting both the irrigant turbulence and the availability of free chlorine ions. This in turn would have reduced the efficacy of the LAI 0.75 W protocol. Swimberghe *et al*, evaluated the efficacy of sonically, ultrasonically, and laser -activated irrigation in removing a biofilm -mimicking hydrogel from the isthmus in a root canal model. Hydrogel removal was highest in the LAI group (90.2%), and was significantly higher than that with UAI, EA, and NI ($P \leq 0.014$), but not significantly different from Eddy ($P = 0.498$). Hydrogel removal with Eddy (85.9%) was significantly higher than that with NI and EA ($P < 0.05$), but not significantly different from UAI ($P = 0.07$). There was no significant difference between the NI and EA group ($P = 1$). Laser -activated irrigation and Eddy resulted in the greatest hydrogel removal, and performed better than EndoActivator and ultrasonically activated irrigation. The effect of laser -activated irrigation was also not dependent on deep intracanal tip placement. A striking fact is that NI, UAI and the sonic activation techniques require canal insertion and the tip to be activated in the vicinity of the isthmus, while the effect of LAI, with the laser tip at the canal entrance, is remote and independent of intracanal tip placement. The effectiveness of the antimicrobial activity of laser activated irrigation may alter, depending on differences in the concentrations and the durations of action of NaOCl in the root canal, and other variables. Thus, it is important to note that the studies' results may have been influenced by these factors. it is difficult to synthesize the results of the above-mentioned studies because of differences in methodology. For example, the biofilm model, the type of irrigant (saline,NaOCl), its concentration (between 1 and 6% NaOCl), the laser wavelength (2780 vs.2940 nm), laser parameters (pulse energy, pulse frequency, position of fibre tip, irradiation time) vary amongst these studies. further studies are required to modify the protocol and standardize the laser parameters to optimize the potential outcomes. Although laser activated irrigation has shown promising preliminary results, caution should be exercised when activating irrigator solutions near the apical constriction.

Results

Cheng *et al.* evaluate the bactericidal effect of Er:YAG laser-activated sodium hypochlorite irrigation (Er:YAG + NaOCl) on biofilms of *Enterococcus faecalis* clinical isolate. The result showed that bacterial reductions in the treatment groups were presented in a descending order of Er:YAG + NaOCl (98.8%), US + NaOCl (98.6%) > NaOCl (94.0%) > Er:YAG + NS (91.9%) > US + NS (78.1%) > NS (51.1%) ($p < 0.05$). The Er:YAG + NaOCl showed an effective bactericidal effect on biofilms of *E. faecalis* isolate, which may be considered an effective protocol for root canal treatment.

Betancourt *et al.* compared the antibacterial effectiveness of 0.5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) activated by the Er,Cr:YSGG laser-activated irrigation (LAI) and passive ultrasonic irrigation (PUI) against a 10-day-old intracanal *Enterococcus faecalis* biofilm. Er,Cr:YSGG LAI proved to be more effective than PUI in enhancing the antimicrobial activity of 0.5% NaOCl against 10-day-old intracanal *E. faecalis* biofilms.

Christo *et al.* establish the antibacterial efficacy of low concentrations of sodium hypochlorite with and without Er,Cr:YSGG laser activation on *Enterococcus faecalis* biofilms in extracted teeth. The results displayed that within the limitations of this laboratory study, low-powered (0.5 W) Er,Cr:YSGG laser activation did not improve the antibacterial effect of low concentrations of sodium hypochlorite. The difference in results may be due to the differing methodology of bacterial contamination; power and duration of laser induced pulse settings and sampling.

Meyer *et al.* evaluated the antimicrobial effect of laser-activated irrigation (LAI) on biofilms formed in simulated root canals. In this study biofilms were formed over 48 h and subsequently subjected to the following treatments, all executed for 20 s: syringe irrigation (SI) with a 27G needle, ultrasonically activated irrigation (UAI) with a size 20 Irrisafe file, and LAI with a 2940 nm Er:YAG laser (20 Hz, 50 ls, 20 or 40 mJ, conical fibre tip at two positions). Tests were performed with both sterile saline as well as NaOCl (2.5%) as the irrigant. The study concluded that laser-activated irrigation removed more biofilm than ultrasonically activated irrigation when using saline as the irrigant, indicating greater physical biofilm removal.

Race *et al.* investigated the efficacy of Er,Cr:YSGG laser and ultrasonic activated irrigation on eradicating a mixed-species biofilm grown in root canals with complex anatomy. The results demonstrated that chemomechanical irrigation with laser and ultrasonic activated irrigation significantly reduced the bacterial load from complex root canal systems; however, there were no significant differences found between the experimental groups.

References

- Swimberghe RCD, De Clercq A, De Moor RJG, Meire MA. Efficacy of sonically, ultrasonically and laser-activated irrigation in removing a biofilm-mimicking hydrogel from an isthmus model. *Int Endod J.* 2019 Apr;52(4):515-523.
- Race J, Zilm P, Ratnayake J, Fitzsimmons T, Marchant C, Cathro P. Efficacy of laser and ultrasonic-activated irrigation on eradicating a mixed-species biofilm in human mesial roots. *Aust Endod J.* 2019 Dec;45(3):317-324
- De Meyer S, Meire MA, Coenye T, De Moor RJ. Effect of laser-activated irrigation on biofilms in artificial root canals. *Int Endod J.* 2017 May;50(5):472-479
- Betancourt P, Merlos A, Sierra JM, Arnabat-Dominguez J, Viñas M. Er,Cr:YSGG Laser-Activated Irrigation and Passive Ultrasonic Irrigation: Comparison of Two Strategies for Root Canal Disinfection. *Photobiomodul Photomed Laser Surg.* 2020 Feb;38(2):91-97
- Christo JE, Zilm PS, Sullivan T, Cathro PR. Efficacy of low concentrations of sodium hypochlorite and low-powered Er,Cr:YSGG laser activated irrigation against an *Enterococcus faecalis* biofilm. *Int Endod J.* 2016 Mar;49(3):279-86.
- Cheng X, Xiang D, He W, Qiu J, Han B, Yu Q, Tian Y. Bactericidal Effect of Er:YAG Laser-Activated Sodium Hypochlorite Irrigation Against Biofilms of *Enterococcus faecalis* Isolate from Canal of Root-Filled Teeth with Periapical Lesions. *Photomed Laser Surg.* 2017 Jul;35(7):386-392.
- Tanaka T, Yahata Y, Handa K, Venkataiah SV, Njuguna MM, Kanehira M, Hasegawa T, Noiri Y, Saito M. An experimental intraradicular biofilm model in the pig for evaluating irrigation techniques. *BMC Oral Health.* 2021 Apr 7;21(1):177.
- Hage W, De Moor RJG, Hajj D, Sfeir G, Sarkis DK, Zogheib C. Impact of Different Irrigant Agitation Methods on Bacterial Elimination from Infected Root Canals. *Dent J (Basel).* 2019 Jun 27;7(3):64.
- Liu T, Huang Z, Ju Y, Tang X. Bactericidal efficacy of three parameters of Nd:YAP laser irradiation against *Enterococcus faecalis* compared with NaOCl irrigation. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2019 Mar;34(2):359-366
- Golob BS, Olivi G, Vrabec M, El Feghali R, Parker S, Benedicenti S. Efficacy of Photon-induced Photoacoustic Streaming in the Reduction of *Enterococcus faecalis* within the Root Canal: Different Settings and Different Sodium Hypochlorite Concentrations. *J Endod.* 2017 Oct;43(10):1730-1735.
- Gergova RT, Gueorgieva T, Dencheva-Garova MS, Krasteva-Panova AZ, Kalchinov V, Mitov I, Kamenoff J. Antimicrobial activity of different disinfection methods against biofilms in root canals. *J Investig Clin Dent.* 2016 Aug;7(3):254-62